

**OBSERVATION AND FEEDBACK: ENHANCING EDUCATIONAL
QUALITY THROUGH COLLABORATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE
HIGHER EDUCATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN**

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***Abstract:** This article examines the use of observation and feedback as a strategic approach to enhancing educational quality. It studies methodologies aimed at advancing teaching and learning by employing teacher observation and systematic feedback. Additionally, the paper underscores the significant outcomes derived from these practices, including improved pedagogical effectiveness and enhanced learning experiences.*

***Keywords:** Observation, feedback, pedagogy, group monitoring, language proficiency.*

Observation is a natural process for all living beings, particularly humans. To put it simply, human activity involves discovering and learning new things about the world through observation. Everyone is an observer from babies to the elderly; people observe each other and learn something simultaneously. However, we must distinguish between everyday observation and observation as a research tool.

We have attempted to define observation as a research tool based on several modern dictionaries. According to the Cambridge Academic Content Dictionary III (2008), observation is defined as “noticing, watching, examining, or interpreting something [1]. Similarly, the Macmillan English Dictionary for Advanced Learners (2002) defines observation as “the process of watching someone or something carefully to find out something [2]. These definitions apply not only to daily life observations but also to observations for educational purposes.

From a methodological perspective, group observation involves examining teachers and students behaviors and specific events within a group by a teacher. Observation is a method of recording and analyzing data, serving as a tool that not only enhances educational oversight but also promotes professional growth among teachers.

Group observation is a collaborative process emphasizing professional development. Both an observed individual and an observer play critical roles before, during, and after the observation. Cooperation at each stage of the process helps both participants benefit from the experience. Group observation supports and monitors teachers and other group staff and contributes to the self-assessment of teachers and

students. It aids recognizing and strengthening good practices, identifying ways to improve teaching and learning, and highlighting practices that need wider dissemination. In all these ways, it significantly impacts the quality of teachers and students learning and experience.

An observer should play a more active role than merely sitting at the back of the classroom. Teachers should do many things: identify discrepancies between intended (or perceived) practice and actual practice, observe the best practices in action, learn from each other, provide detailed and specific evidence compared to other sources of information, enhance understanding for improved teaching, and use effective models.

Group observation should always be accompanied by feedback, as it completes the observation process. Feedback is a complex area within teaching and learning because providing feedback to students and teachers is not the same and depends on the skills being learned (reading, writing, speaking, listening). For example, in a writing course, there are specific ways to give feedback on students writing.

Our research explored feedback as a method to enhance language competence among teachers and students. It is well-known that feedback aims to influence improvement in teaching and learning. We defined feedback as per various sources: the Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English (1995) defines feedback as “advice, criticism, etc., about how successful or useful something is [3]. The Macmillan English Dictionary for Advanced Learners (2002) describes feedback as “comments about how well or badly someone is doing something, intended to help them do it better [2].

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